

Machine Learning Leveraged Weighted Consensus Model for Blockchain Based Large-scale E-Voting

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Abstract— The growth of blockchain-based systems has permitted researchers to create next-generation e-voting systems. The Proof-of-Work consensus algorithm, which is the traditional blockchain consensus method, has a major impact on energy consumption and degrades the system's scalability, efficiency, and latency. It is used in Bitcoin. In order to overcome the aforementioned issues and secure e-voting systems, we suggest in this study a hybrid consensus model which made up of Proof of Credibility and Proof of Stake that cooperate with one another. In order to guarantee the accuracy of the voting results, smart contracts are utilised to create a safe computing environment and a reliable public message board. In addition, our research produced fresh findings about the general performance, security, and scalability of blockchain-based electronic voting systems.

Keywords— Blockchain, E-Voting, Proof of Shake (PoS), Proof of Credibility (PoC), Large-scale Voting

I. INTRODUCTION

In a democracy, the people have a voice via the voting process. Experts agree that paper ballots are the safest and most reliable approach to ensure that every eligible voter may exercise their franchise [1]. But it's easy to make errors or take advantage of this method. As technology has progressed, contemporary voters have the unique ability to exercise their democratic right and responsibility online[2], monitor the status of their votes, verify the exact moment they were cast, and find out when their votes will be tallied. Additionally, electronic voting fraud, such as the manipulation of absentee ballots cast remotely, is widespread in modern elections. North Carolina's 2019 election issue [3] and Georgia's 2017 server wipe [4] are two recent instances of such claims. Research has shown that election outcomes may be swayed by exploiting the weaknesses of centralized ballot storage in electronic voting systems. And that might lead to a crisis level of disillusionment among the electorate [5,6].

As can be seen in Figure 1, blockchain technology has garnered a great deal of interest and is already being implemented in a wide range of enterprise software used in a variety of industries [7], including crypto currency [8], supply chain management [9], healthcare [10], smart contracts [11], and financial services [12]. Like paper ballots, every electronic vote can be verified and monitored thanks to blockchain technology's use in e-voting systems. Succeed in doing with older electronic voting systems [13, 14]. A growing body of literature [15–17] has emerged in support of blockchain-based electronic voting systems. The research community agrees that these platforms are public, open, transparent, and verifiable. However, it is difficult to ascertain whether or not these systems genuinely exhibit the

claimed properties due to the absence of actual system structures.

Figure 1 : Blockchain applications

To construct decentralized autonomous voting systems that can remove as many human influences as feasible, numerous notable researches have also recommended the usage of a smart contract [18–20]. In our last review [21], this study focused on a few of recent contributions that dealt with the privacy and safety concerns of a blockchain-based electronic voting system. In what is perhaps the most important aspect of a democratic society, the ability to vote electronically, blockchain technology delivers all the features necessary for such a system. The events that have already occurred cannot be altered, and the ongoing occurrences cannot be hacked, thanks to the blockchain technology. Additionally, the system does not accept modifications. The same outcomes are shown across all authorized devices/nodes, and voters' identities are protected while yet being able to be tracked for each vote. Bitcoin [22] was the first and is now the most widely used digital currency, and its introduction essentially kicked off the blockchain revolution. Further, when a new block is formed and attached to the existing one, a special mechanism is needed to solve a computationally costly problem known as Proof-of-Work (PoW) [23]. However, PoW is wasteful with energy and affects throughput and transaction delay, which in turn affects scalability and performance [24]. Consequently, Proof of Stake (PoS) has emerged as a formidable rival to PoW in light of its success in avoiding those pitfalls [24]. To be more specific, under the PoS consensus method, a group of validators takes turns proposing and voting on the next block, and the value of the staked tokens determines the weight of the vote. Like PoW, PoS provide the network with an undeniable monetary boost, allowing it to function efficiently while lowering the possibility of conspiracy or assault. To get around PoW's computational complexity, though, and hence its energy inefficiency, this alternative method is used. Since then, the

hybrid consensus model has gained a lot of attention as a possible solution to the problems with the PoW consensus approach [25].

Also, studies have been conducted on how to improve blockchain speed and scalability using the shading technique [26,27]. The most common method for getting around this scalability problem is shading, which involves splitting the network into many smaller pieces. These pieces, or shards, may conduct separate transactions and keep separate ledgers, all while working in simultaneously. In this research, these studies focus on improving upon existing blockchain-based electronic voting systems. It was interesting to find out that nobody has published a standard list of system requirements.

Because of this, this study decided to look at electronic voting again and offer a hybrid consensus methodology to make sure it's safe. Our concept, BEV model, is predicated on a hybrid consensus mechanism

II. RELATED WORK

Initial efforts to develop blockchain-based electronic voting protocols gave rise to bitcoin incentive structures. Zhao and Chan presented a mechanism for Bitcoin voting that enables n financed voters to choose one of two candidates by sending Bitcoin, drawing inspiration from a lottery protocol [10]. In their work, randomly generated numbers that are circulated are used to disguise ballots. Voters make off-chain commitments to the random number and the disguised ballot before making their commitments public via Bitcoin. However, their system is constrained by approval elections (single "Yes/No" voting type) and offers no genuine anonymity for voters owing to Bitcoin's pseudonymity. These two shortcomings are both improved. Takabatake et al. suggested using Zerocoin, a Bitcoin laundering extension that offers anonymity, to build voting systems. Tian et al. used a subroutine from Zhao and Chan's protocol to demonstrate that voting in Bitcoin is not limited to binary types. Other financial incentive e-voting systems, including [7,11], use various cryptographic primitives in their constructions, like anonymous Kerberos and Circle Shuffle, which has enhanced and extended the characteristics of blockchain voting, like end-to-end verifiability and efficiency. E-voting systems with financial incentives often provide refunds or rewards for legitimate voters while punishing dishonest ones after an election.

Although it appears sensible, this method actually promotes divergence from the norm and lowers voting participation. The motives are divided into two categories. Voters may choose not to pay the significant transaction charge up front for a possible reward during the first half. On the other hand, voters are more inclined to accept the financial penalty when vote-buyers have promised bigger rewards. Additionally, monetary incentive schemes are unworkable for extensive national elections owing to the high cost. As a result, several electronic voting systems now see the blockchain as a secure and open voting mechanism. Verifiable voting methods used to depend on complex cryptographic structures, but today's blockchain technology may be able to overcome this restriction.

According to separate arguments made by Chaieb et al. [16] and Pawlak et al., blockchain may and should be employed in e-voting systems to provide universal verifiability and transparent audit ability. As part of their BEV efforts, certain for-profit firms, like TIVI, FollowMyVote, and Agora [2], also deploy the blockchain as a public voting system. They claim that their systems are openly available, scalable, anonymous, and verifiable. However, it is difficult to assess whether or not their solutions really attain the advertised qualities since their technical documentation and white papers lack realistic system structures.

The BEV is improved with the introduction of blockchain technology via smart contracts [27]. Smart contracts are digital agreements whose terms are upheld automatically and which may be used to conduct elections without the intervention of a dependable administrator. McCorry et al. [21] developed a boardroom (i.e., small scale) self-tallying e-voting mechanism, which is implemented as a smart contract on the Ethereum blockchain. This protocol was based on Open Vote Network [25]. Despite offering the highest level of voter anonymity, their electronic voting system is not strong enough to ward off a Denial-of-Service (DoS) assault. Additionally, the voting scale is limited to 50–60 voters due to a constraint of the Ethereum platform. Shading-style [22,28] and EOS-style [26] blockchains have recently been suggested, which overcome the obstacle of a slow block production rate and transaction rate. Using smart contracts to create a safe voting system without worrying about blockchain itself was proposed by Yu et al. [27]. (i.e., platform-independence). Their homomorphic encryption and linkable ring signature-based solution has been shown to be scalable and capable of withstanding a variety of well-known attacks.

III. PROPOSED WORK

This section outlines proposed system architecture, Interaction between the entities and usecase diagram for blockchain based large-scale E-voting system.

A. Large-scale E-voting system

This section gives a general description of our extensive blockchain-based electronic voting system, including interactions between various entities, as depicted in Figure 2. Each voter needs a smart phone or computer as their primary piece of technology. Each voter has a wallet that contains their unique user information. In addition, each voter is given a digital currency, which stands in for one vote. To identify and assess the security, scalability, and performance challenges in blockchain-based systems, we chose the e-voting system as an example case.

Blockchain technology will be used to establish a decentralized architecture, enhance openness and integrity, and create a voting process that can be independently verified. Additionally, we sought to improve the voting procedure's speed, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

Figure 2: Architecture of the e-voting system based on blockchain

Manage servers (MS): The purpose of (MS) is to supply nodes with certificates, store node knowledge in the bottom blockchain network, and broadcast it to the upper blockchain network. This enables node authentication and contains user credentials for system login.

Blockchain network: The suggested e-voting blockchain network consists of several blockchains operating concurrently. Due to the parallel execution capabilities provided by this structure, the system's performance and scalability are enhanced. Given that each node in private chains has a local blockchain which holds the privacy-sensitive data, the lower chains (also known as private chains) are used to store voter identity information and node information. After certain voters successfully concur on the transactions, a procedure known as proof-of-stake consensus, and simultaneously process transactions, the upper-chain (public blockchain like Ethereum) is used to maintain distinct blockchain states among all voters. The upper-(public chain's blockchain's) recorded transactions are reliable and unchangeable. The upper-chain and lower-chain routing management is the same as it was in the prior report.

Users (voters): Users can use the identification to verify and access their wallets; they are voters and members of the election committee. Voters are given a digital token with which they can vote. As a result, the blockchain's top layer is where smart contracts are implemented (Ethereum blockchain).

Blockchain contract (smart contract): The suggested decentralized system employs smart contracts, which are pieces of code that run on their own. The functions built into smart contracts provide the contractual arrangements that allow the top layer transactions in the public blockchain to be monitored. In our scenario, each blockchain node can independently execute the smart contract to reach a consensus, leading to the development of a modular cryptosystem for electronic voting systems.

B. use case daigram

Here, the administrator must first log in before creating an election, adding users, and allowing users to vote. The administrator can view the results after the voting has been completed.

Figure 3: Use case diagram of the proposed system

IV. RESULTS

The implementation of the proposed system consists of six phases: Login phase, Admin phase, create election phase, add use phase, vote phase, and results phase.

The first page is the login page that requires the user and admin credentials as mentioned in figure 4. after admin authenticate themselves, the page is redirected to admin phase. The navigation bar appears on the left of the page. This bar must navigate the admin to other functions such as show home, category list, voter list, users and logout as shown in figure 5.

Online Voting System

Figure 4: Login phase

Figure 7: add user phase

Figure 5: Admin phase

Figure 8: Vote phase

Figure 6: create election phase

Figure 9: Results phase

Admin can create the election by clicking on voting list and fill the form as shown in figure 6. figure 7 depicts new user form for creating new user. The vote phase can automatically redirect when users can login their credentials. In this vote phase the voter can select a candidate and press the submit button to send a vote once the vote has been confirmed as shown in figure 8. Figure 9 depicts the election results.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

To evaluate the efficacy of the proposed model, an experimental setup was built in MATLAB using origin lab, and simulation experiments were run on Amazon EC2. For t2.medium type as a single node with CPU = 2 and RAM (GiB) = 4, the simulated network size varied from 200 to 1000. The experiment compared the proposed model's throughput and latency to those of established consensus

techniques like PoS and PoW in order to gauge its scalability and assess its performance. In this research, we first expanded a simulated network with 200 nodes in each cluster to a full-fledged 1000-node network.

Figure 10: latency of proposed & existing models

Figure 11: Throughput of proposed & existing models

In this investigation, we monitored the throughput and evaluated the delay for 10 different blocks. Second, this research tested both the PoW and PoS protocols on a single simulated network, with the number of nodes (the network size) varying from 200 to 1000. The delay of 10 PoW blocks and 10 PoS blocks was evaluated in this investigation. Figure 10 illustrates a contrast between the current consensus approaches (PoW and PoS) and the suggested consensus model (PoC & PoS model). Data bars indicate that the PoW consensus technique had the most delay at about 63 seconds, while the PoS consensus method had the shortest at around 10 seconds. The planned BC E-voting system has a delay of about 27 seconds. Figure 11 further shows that the transaction processing speed of both PoW and PoS remained constant as the number of nodes in the network increased. To counter this, the suggested model handled more transactions as the number of nodes grew. When the number of nodes was raised to 1000, the throughput of the proposed model surpassed 60 Tps, which was more than the throughput of both PoW (5 Tps) and PoS (25 Tps). As a consequence, the outcome verifies the scalability of the suggested PoC & PoS model.

VI. CONCLUSION

E-voting is a potential answer to the youthful, tech-savvy population's lack of interest in voting. Due to election fraud and corruption that took place in the current system. Using blockchain technology could be a solution to make electronic voting more open, transparent, and independently auditable. This study examines the possibilities of blockchain technology and how it may be used in an electronic voting system. For large-scale elections, a novel blockchain-enabled voting system is presented in this study that satisfies requirements for cost-effectiveness, verifiability, resilience, and other factors. The technology is implemented as blockchain-based smart contracts that operate. In this research, we introduced the PSC-Bchain, a hybrid consensus model that combines Proof of Credibility (PoC) with Proof of Stake (PoS). Due to this, a safe hybrid blockchain was developed, which guarantees comprehensive security when used with the electronic voting system. In terms of possible future work, we would have to assure coercion resistance and reception freedom by constructing the vote for the user using a randomizer token, which is a tamper-resistant source of randomness that works as a black box

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